

(I Plate)

B. DATTA, NEW DELHI AND C. L. SUBI, MYSORE.

The inscription, edited below with the kind permission of the Chief Epigraphist, was found at Garh in the Alwar District of Rajasthan. It has been noticed in *Indian Archaeology* 1961-62—'A Review',¹ as well as in the *Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy* for 1961-62². The original slab which was lying for sometime with Dr. B. Ch. Chhabra³, the then Joint Director General of Archaeology in India, (now professor of Ancient Indian History and Culture, Panjab University, Chandigarh) is now preserved in the National Museum, New Delhi. It is in two pieces of almost equal size, due to a vertical break in its centre. Both the pieces joined together cover an area about 79 cm × 50 cm. The inscription is engraved leaving a margin of 2 to 3 cm on all sides. It consists of 19 lines of writing which is carefully and boldly executed and which is in a good state of preservation with the exception of some damaged letters along the breach in the middle and a few others here and there. The average size of the letters is roughly 2 cms.

The characters belong to the Kuṭila variety of the Proto-Nāgarī alphabet of about the tenth century. Of the initial vowels, *a* (lines 2, 19), *ā* (lines 6, 10, 13, 14) and *i* (lines 6, 16, 17, 18) occur in the record. Medial *ā* is indicated by a vertical stroke to the right of the letters but in some letters like *jā* (line 14), *ṭā* (line 6) and *ṇā* (line 5) it is indicated by a downward curved stroke rising upwards to the right. The form of medial *u* in *ru* (line 15, etc.) is interesting as it is indicated differently in conjunction with other consonants. Medial *ē* and *ō* have invariably been indicated by a *śirōmātrā* except once in *°dēva* (line 10) where *ē* is indicated by a downward curved stroke to the left. On the other hand, medial *ai* and *au* have been indicated by a curved stroke at the top and a downward curved stroke to the left of the letters except in *°janair°* (line 1) and *=asau* (line 4) where two curved strokes at the top have been used. The *anusvāra* and *visargas* are indicated respectively by one and two hollow circles in the first two lines, while in the remaining lines the hollow circles are changed to dots. The forms of subscript *ṇa*, subscript *ñ* and subscript *tu* are interesting. The subscript *ṇ* in *rṇṇa* (line 1, etc.) lies on its side and its form is not distinguishable from that of subscript *ñ* (*Jñāna*, line 2) and subscript *tu* (*vāstu*, line 8). The form of the symbol for *ōm* (line 17) is also noteworthy.

The language of the record is Sanskrit and the whole of the text with the exception of the initial *Om namō = 'rhatē* and the portion recording the date in line 17, has been composed in beautiful verses embellished with a profuse use of the various figures of speech. These verses, apart from their historical value, present an elegant style of ornate poetry. The record has been written and inscribed with great care for the number of omissions and commissions is small. The employment of the letter *v* for both *v* and *b*, the reduplication of the

¹ Indian Archaeology, 1961-62, A Review p.85, Serial No. 63.

² A.R.Ep., 1961-62, App. B. No. 128.

³ We are thankful to Dr. Chhabra for allowing us to edit the epigraph. He has also helped us in translating some of the difficult passages in the record.

consonants following *r*, with the exception of *th* in *arthi* (line 4) and of *m* in *sandhi* in *sindhur* = *makara* in line 16 contrary to the reduplication of the consonant *v* in *sandhi* in *bhūpatir* = *vvijayatām*, and the frequent use of the *avagraha* may be noted as the orthographical peculiarities of the record. The word *Sāgaranandi* has been either mis-spelt as *Sāgaraṇandī* or else it has been taken to be a single *pada* being a personal name to effect the change of *na* into *ṇa*. It may also be noted that the *sandhi* in *Śakrālayam ārōḍhum* (line 4) has not been observed.

The date of the epigraph is given in line 17 as Samvat 979¹, Vaiśākha badi 13, Bhauma. It regularly corresponds to 921 A. D.,² May 8, Tuesday.

The inscription opens with a salutation to the *Arhat*, and the first two verses (verse 1-2) are devoted to Jinendra Śāntinātha mentioning all his virtuous qualities. In the following verse (verse 3) a certain king Mahīpāla, whose feet were adored by a host of feudatories, is introduced. The fourth verse introduces the ruling chief Sāvaṭa. He has been compared with the *Mahābhārata* heroes Karṇa and Bhīma, in philanthropy and valour, respectively and his person is stated to be endowed with the auspicious marks (*lakshmaṇ-ānvita-tanu*)³. In the following three verses (verses 5-7) we are introduced to a certain Sarvadēva, son of Dēddulaka, and grandson of Ārdraṭa⁴ born in the Dharkkaṭa family hailing from Pūrṇatallaka. He is stated to have built a beautiful Jaina temple for Śāntinātha in the city of **Siṃhapadra**. In the following verse (verse 8), Sarvadēva has been compared with Viśvakarmā, the divine architect. It is stated that by virtue of his skill in the art of architecture his fame enveloped the three worlds and that he was held in high esteem by the assembly of architects. The following two verses (verses 9-10) state that the great king Pulindra who had realised the transitory nature of the world called Sarvadēva who, at his instance, made a lofty image of Śāntidēva and installed it at Rājyapura. In the 11th verse, Sarvadēva is also credited to have erected a stone house, i.e. a temple. The next two verses (verses 12-13), describe the magnificence and excellence of this temple. This is followed by a statement (verses 14-15) that the temple together with a permanent endowment for worship, was entrusted to the learned *āchārya* Śūrasēna and to the *gōshṭhikas* (i.e. members of a *gōshṭhī*), who were merchants and were devoted to the *Āchārya*. The next verse (verse 16) records a wish that the temple may endure as long as the Jaina Dharma, the Mēru mountain and the sea exist. Verse 17 mentions the two famous poets Sāgaraṇandi and Lōkadēva as the co-authors of the *praśasti*. Then follows the date discussed above and a particular symbol intended to mark the end of the record.

The above is immediately followed by another record which is in the nature of a supplement to the first. Of this only four complete and one incomplete verses have been preserved. The first verse refers to a mighty earthquake which shook (literally uprooted) even the lofty mountains as also toppled this temple down. The second verse introduces the wise Varāṅga, son of Sarvadēva as the chief of the architects. Next two verses (verses 3-4) speak of his

¹ Cf. *Indian Archaeology* 1959-60- A Review, p. 74, No.56, where the date is wrongly given as 'Samvat 919'.

² The date is given in the current year 979 which is equal to expired 978; Cf. Swami Kannu Pillai's *An Indian Ephemerics*, Vol.II, p.244. However, if the year is taken to be Kārttikādi, the date would correspond to 923 A.D. April 15, f. d.t. 84; cf. *A.R.Ep.*, 1961-62, No.B 128 where the equivalent has been given according to the *Kārttikādi* reckoning, but the day has been wrongly given as Wednesday.

³ The pun used here on the words *lakshmaṇ-ānvita-tanu* is noteworthy. Could it also suggest that Sāvaṭa had a brother by name Lakshmaṇa who was generally by his side and gave him a helping hand in administration? But we do not know of any Lakshmaṇa from the political history of the region and period under question.

⁴ This name has been read as Ārbhaṭa in *Indian Archaeology* 1961-62.—A Review, p. 85, No. 63.

beauty, eloquence, wisdom, philanthropy and above all of his adeptness in the science of architecture. The fifth verse which is incomplete states that he was a rich man, perhaps the chief of the architects, and that he was honoured by the king. The record ends here abruptly¹.

The object of this supplementary inscription seems to be that Varāṅga renovated or reconstructed the temple after it was affected by the earthquake. The calligraphic similarities of the two records coupled with the reference to the destruction of the temple by the earthquake in the second record, suggest that both the records were engraved simultaneously and that the first record is only a copy of the original set up by Sarvadēva on the date mentioned at its end. As the extent portion of the second record is not dated, it is not possible to ascertain as to when exactly this slab containing the two records was put up.

Mahīpāla whose feet are stated to have been worshipped by a host of feudatories (*sāmanta-chakra-vihitādara-pāda-sēvaḥ*) was undoubtedly a suzerain king. This is also confirmed by the mention in the inscription of a ruler (*bhūpati*) named Sāvata who must have been a feudatory of Mahīpāla. A sovereign king named Mahīpāla is known to have been ruling at least during 914-17 A.D.² He has been identified with the Gurjara-Pratihāra king Mahīpāla (I). As our record belongs nearly to the same time and mentions Mahīpāla as a sovereign king, there seems to be no doubt in his being identical with the Gurjara-Pratihāra king Mahīpāla I. This is also corroborated by the fact that the feudatory princes ruling at Rājyapura where a temple was built according to our inscription, acknowledged the sovereignty of the Gurjara-Pratihāras as late as V.S. 1096 (960 A.D.), the date of the Rajōrgaḍh inscription of Mathanadēva. If this identification is accepted, the last known date of the Gurjara-Pratihāra king Mahīpāla which was fixed by the Asni inscription as 917 A.D. would be extended upto 921 A.D., the date of the present inscription.

The Rajōr inscription³ referred to above mentions a certain *Mahārājādhirāja Sāvata* of the Gurjara-Pratihāra family as the father of the ruling chief *Mahārājādhirāja Paramēśvara* Mathanadēva who was residing at Rājyapura. The latter was a feudatory of the *Paramabhaṭṭāraka Mahārājādhirāja Paramēśvara* Vijayapāladēva who meditated on the feet of the *Paramabhaṭṭāraka Mahārājādhirāja Paramēśvara* Kshitipāladēva. Prof. Kielhorn who edited the inscription takes Vijayapāla and Kshitipāla as the kings of the Imperial Gurjara-Pratihāra family. As seen above, Sāvata of our epigraph was also a feudatory of the same family and was ruling over the Rājyapura region only thirty-nine years before the date of the Rajōr inscription of Mathanadēva. He, therefore, appears to be identical with *Mahārājādhirāja Sāvata*, the father of Mathanadēva.

Now, if Vijayapāla and Mathanadēva were contemporaries, their fathers or immediate predecessors, i.e. Kshitipāla and Sāvata, could also have been contemporaries. Our inscription which mentions Sāvata as a contemporary of Mahīpāla who was also known by the

¹ That the slab is not broken away at the bottom is evident from the ornamental designs in its lower margin. It is likely that the remaining portion of the second record was engraved on another slab which is not yet available.

² Cf. the Asni stone inscription dated V.S.974(=917 A.D.) (*Ind. Ant.* Vol.XVI, pp. 173 ff) and the Haḍḍālā grant dated Śaka 838(=914 A.D.) (*ibid.*, Vol.XII, pp. 193 ff. and Vol. XVIII, pp. 90-91). While the Asni inscription describes Mahīpāla as a *Paramabhaṭṭāraka Mahārājādhirāja Paramēśvara* the Haḍḍālā grant describes him as *Rājādhirāja Paramēśvara*.

³ Above, Vol. III, pp. 263 ff.

synonymous name of Kshitipāla¹ may lend support to this view. Kshitipāla of the Rajōr inscription would, therefore, appear to be identical with Mahipāla I of the present epigraph.

However, difficulties in the way of the identification suggested above arise due to the existence of a number of intervening kings who are believed to belong to the Gurjara-Pratihāra family. They are : (1) Vināyakapāla,² known from his Bengal Asiatic Society's Copper-plate³ dated V.S. 988 (931 A.D.), (2) Mahēndrapāla (II) of Pratabgarh stone inscription⁴ dated V.S. 1003 (946 A.D.) wherein he is described as the son of Vināyakapāla ; (3) Dēvapāla who according to the Siyaḍōṇi inscription, was the son of Kshitipāla, and ruled in V.S. 1005 (948-49 A.D.) ; (4) Vināyakapāla (II) who in the Khajuraho inscription,⁵ dated V.S. 1011 (953-54 A.D.) and belonging to the time of the Chandella king Dhaṅga is stated to be ruling over the earth ; and (5) Mahipāla (II) of the Bayana Ukhā-mandir inscription⁶ dated V.S. 1012 (956 A.D.) of the queen Chitralēkhā. Mahipāla II was succeeded in 960 A.D. by Vijayapāla, son of Kshitipāla, of the Rajōr inscription. With as many as five kings intervening between Mahipāla I and Vijayapāla, it is difficult to identify the latter's father Kshitipāla with Mahipāla I. It may be assumed that like Mahipāla I, Mahipāla II was also known by the synonymous name of Kshitipāla which has been used in the Rajōr inscription. Kshitipāla of the Rajōr inscription may, therefore, be identified with Mahipāla (II).

It may, however, be pointed out that some scholars do not consider the five intervening kings as distinct rulers. Bhandarkar, for instance, identifies Vināyakapāla I with Mahipāla I *alias* Kshitipāla, Mahēndrapāla II with Dēvapāla and Vināyakapāla II with Mahipāla II *alias* Kshitipāla.⁷ Dr. N. Ray, on the other hand, distinguishes Vināyakapāla I from Mahipāla I whom he identifies with Bhōja II. According to him Dēvapāla was the son of Mahipāla I *alias* Kshitipāla while Vināyakapāla II and Mahipāla II were the sons of Mahēndrapāla II and Dēvapāla respectively⁸. Dr. Tripathi while accepting the identity of Mahipāla I *alias* Kshitipāla I *alias* Vināyakapāla I takes Mahipāla II to be a vassal chief and not as a Pratihāra king⁹. Thus, according to the chronology of the later Pratihāras proposed by Dr. Bhandarkar and Dr. Ray, Vijayapāla's father Kshitipāla *alias* Mahipāla II was the grandson of Mahipāla I *alias* Kshitipāla. He, therefore, cannot be identical with the latter. But Dr. Tripathi who does not consider Mahipāla II as a Pratihāra king, takes Vijayapāla to be a brother or half brother of Dēvapāla, son of Kshitipāla. Thus, according to him Vijayapāla's father Kshitipāla is no other than Mahipāla I *alias* Kshitipāla. We have already seen above that the evidence of our inscription seems to lend some support to the identification of Kshitipāla of the Rajōr inscription with Mahipāla I. However, the possibility of Vijayapāla's father Kshitipāla being identical with Mahipāla II cannot be completely ignored, for the available evidence is insufficient to prove or disprove any of the identifications.

¹ See, above, Vol. I, p. 171.

² He was identified with Mahipāla (I) by some scholars but this identification has been opposed by some other scholars who believe them to be two different persons. For all the views, see Prof. N. Ray's article entitled 'A note on the chronology of the later Pratihāras', published in *Ind. Ant.*, Vol. LVII, pp. 230 ff.

³ *Ind. Ant.*, Vol. XV, pp. 138 ff.

⁴ Above, Vol. XIV, pp. 180 ff.

⁵ *Ibid.*, Vol. I, pp. 162 ff.

⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 122 ff.

⁷ Bhandarkar's list, p. 400.

⁸ *Ind. Ant.*, Vol. LVII, p. 234.

⁹ Tripathi, *History of Kanauj*, pp. 274-75.

The inscription under study mentions a certain Pulindra who is described as a great king in verse 10. This verse does not tell anything about this king except that he brought the renowned architect Sarvadēva who installed a big image of Śāntinātha at Rājyapura. As the Rājyapura region was being ruled over by Sāvata, there is no possibility of another king ruling over the same territory. Further, the fact that Pulindra is described as a great king precludes the possibility of his being a subordinate of Sāvata. The only possibility is that Pulindra was a secondary name of Sāvata¹ for only the latter could have brought the architect Sarvadēva to construct a temple at Rājyapura.

Our inscription mentions two famous poets Sāgaranandin and Lōkadēva as the authors of the *prāsasti*. While the latter is not known from any other source, a poet named Sāgaranandin is known as the author of the *Nāṭakalakṣhaṇaratnakōśa* and probably of a play named *Jānakīharāṇa*. Sylvain Levi², who discovered the manuscript of the *Nāṭakalakṣhaṇaratnakōśa*, and M. Ramakrishna Kavi³ have both shown that Sāgaranandin was earlier than Dhanañjaya. The latter was a contemporary of the Paramāra Vākpatirāja (II) Muñja (A.D. 974-994) during whose reign he is known to have composed the *Kārikās*. Hence the date of Dhanañjaya being the later half of the tenth century, Sāgaranandin has to be placed earlier than that. Again, the fact that the *Nāṭakalakṣhaṇaratnakōśa* contains quotations from Rājaśekhara's *Viddhaśālabhañjikā* and the *Karpūramañjarī* proves that Sāgaranandin flourished later than Rājaśekhara who is known to be a contemporary of the Pratihāra kings Mahēndrapāla (I) (A.D. 893-907) and Mahipāla (I)⁵. But Sāgaranandin of our inscription was a contemporary of Mahipāla (I) and consequently of Rājaśekhara also. However, as the latter claims himself to be a *guru* of Mahēndrapāla he must have been a very old man, if at all he was living, at the time of our inscription. On the other hand, Sāgaranandin of our record, who composed even this short *prāsasti* jointly with Lōkadēva, seems to have been a young poet who in spite of his claim of being famous, was not yet very well established. He was possibly a junior contemporary of Rājaśekhara (c.875 to 925 A.D.) and belonged approximately to the first half of the 10th century. This date would admirably suit Sāgaranandin, the author of *Nāṭakalakṣhaṇaratnakōśa*, who was earlier than Dhanañjaya and later than Rājaśekhara. Sāgaranandin, of our record may, therefore, be identical with Sāgaranandin, the author of *Nāṭakalakṣhaṇaratnakōśa*.

Now, Sāgaranandin seems to have belonged to some part of eastern India.⁶ As our inscription comes from the Western part of India, the identity of the two Sāgaranandins may be questioned. This does not seem to be a very strong ground to set aside the conclusion

¹ It is also possible to take Pulindra as another name of Mahipāla (I) who was the overlord of Sāvata and who probably bore several names like Vināyakaṭpāla, Hērampāla, Harsha, Chaṇḍapāla and Kārttikēya (*Ind. Ant.*, Vol. LXII, p. 202 and footnotes).

² *Journal Asiatique*, cciii (1923), p. 210.

³ *New Indian Antiquary*, Vol. II, pp. 412 ff.

⁴ *The Age of Imperial Kanauj*, p. 195.

⁵ The *Bālabhārata* or *Prachanda-Pāṇḍava*, a fragmentary play ascribed to Rājaśekhara, contains a verse which states that the play was enacted before an assemblage of guests invited by a king of the lineage of Raghu, whose name was Mahipāla and who was the son of a king whose *biruda* or title was Nirbhayanarēndra and who was the paramount sovereign of Āryāvarta. Further, Rājaśekhara, in all his four extant plays, declares himself to be the spiritual teacher (*guru* or *upādhyāya*) of a king Mahēndrapāla or Nirbhayarāja. Both Mahēndrapāla *alias* Nirbhayanarēndra and Mahipāla have been identified with the Pratihāra kings Mahēndrapāla (I) and his son, Mahipāla (I) respectively, (Cf. *The Age of Imperial Kanauj*, pp. 33 and 180).

⁶ See *Journal Asiatique*, Vol. ccii (1923) p. 212. Levi considers Sāgaranandin to be a descendant of the family of Nandins mentioned in the Gaya inscription. (*Ind. Ant.*, Vol. X, pp. 343 ff.). He has been quoted mostly by the writers who inhabited Oḍhra, East Magadha, Gauḍa, Kāmarūpa and Dakṣiṇa Kōśala countries and who probably belonged to or were the followers of the Eastern School of rhetoric (*New Indian Antiquary*, Vol. II, p. 419).

reached above, particularly because no specific place has been mentioned in the epigraph to which Sāgaranandin belonged. The latter might not necessarily be a local man; he might have belonged to some place in eastern India, in which case he might have composed the record and sent it to Rājyapura (Rajōr in Alwar District of Rajasthan).

The Dharkata-jāti to which Ārdrata, the father of Dēddulaka and the grandfather of Sarvadēva, is stated to have belonged is known from many records¹. The Sakrai stone inscription² dated V.S. 699 provides the earliest instance of the mention of the Dharkata caste. It is interesting to note that in our inscription the Dharkata-jāti is stated to have hailed from a place called Pūrṇatallaka mentioned in the Bijolia inscription³ which has been identified by Dr. Dasharatha Sharma with Pūntalā in the Jodhpur state of Rajasthan⁴.

Of the place-names mentioned in our record, Pūrṇatallaka has been identified above. The place named Siṅhapadra where Sarvadēva is stated to have built a beautiful Jaina temple cannot be identified⁵. Rājyapura where a temple was built and an image of Śānti-Jina was installed by Sarvadēva, is also mentioned in the Rajōr inscription of Mathanadēva. It has been identified with Rajōr or Rajōrgaḍh, or rather with Paranagar, close to the modern village of Rajōr in Alwar District of Rajasthan.

TEXT⁶

[Metres: Verses 1, 4, 10, 13 *Śārdūlavikrīḍita*; verses 2, 8 *Sragdharā*; verses 3, 5, 7 *Vasanta-tilakā*; verses 6, 11, 14-15, 18-21 *Anuṣṭubh*; verse 9 *Upajāti*; verses 12, 16 *Mandākrāntā* verse 17 *Āryā*.]

- 1 Ōm namō='rhatē || Śrī[mān=yō] mṛiga-lānchhanō='pi sakalaḥ śaśvat=kalaṅk-ōjjhitō nishkāmō='[p]i [vi]tirṇṇa-bhavya-vibhavō ' yaḥ pūrṇa-kāmō='bhavat | datt-ārghō='pi nirantaram vu(bu)dha-janair=yo='nargha-
- 2 tām yātavān=sa śrēyāṅsi(msi) samādadhātu bhavatām Śāntir=Jinēndraḥ sadā||[1*] Avyād=vaḥ Śāntināthaḥ smara-śara-nikar-ālakshya-vakshō='ngabhāsi Lōkālōk=āva-lōka-sphuṭa-hatad=amala-jñāna-
- 3 [sā]mrājya-sampat | bhakty=āyāt-ānat-Ēndra-ślatha-mukuṭa-taṭ-ōtk ṛiṣṭa-ratn-ōtkar=ārchchir-mmālā-vidyōtit-āṅghṛir=ghanatara-durit-ārāti-nirṇṇāsa-dakshaḥ|| [2*]Yasya pratāpa-śikhinō jvalataḥ sphuranti
- 4 tārā-chchhalēna ra[ja]nīm paritaḥ sphuliṅgāḥ | jiyād=asau bhuvi chiram Mahi-pāladēvaḥ s[ā]manta-chakra-vihit-ādara⁷-pāda-sēvaḥ|| [3*] Tyāgēn=ārthi-manōrathān=saphalayan=Karṇṇāyatē yō='nisām ni-
- 5 ghanan=Kaurava-sam[bhṛi]tam parava(ba)lam Bhimāyatē yō ranē | sarvattr=āpi cha Lakshman-ānvita-tanū Rāmāyatē yō bhṛiśam sa sri-Sāvata-bhūpatir=vvijayatām prakhyāta-kirttiś=chiram|| [4*] Śrī-Pūrṇatallaka-

¹ Cf. PRAS, WC, 1908, p. 37, above, Vol. XXXIV, p. 80, and ibid., Vol. XIX, pp. 58, text-line 3 where *Dharakkata-Jātiya* is wrongly read as *Varkkata-jātiya*.

² Above, Vol. XXVII, p. 32.

³ Ibid., Vol. XXVI, p. 97.

⁴ *Early Chauhan Dynasties*, p. 23.

⁵ It is apparently different from Siṃhagōshṭha, a place mentioned in the Harsha stone inscription of Vyāghrarāja (above, Vol. II pp. 119 ff.) which has been identified by D. R. Bhandarkar with Sinhot (*Ind. Ant.* Vol. XLII., p. 60).

⁶ From the original stone and impressions.

⁷ The letter *ra* was first omitted inadvertently and was inserted later on between *da* and *pā*.

- 6 vinirggata-Dharkkaṭ-ākhyā-jātau sa Ārdraṭa=iti prathitō va(ba)bhūva | yō=nēkaśō
vividha-śilpa-vikalpanāsu nishṇāta-dhīr=dṛishadi Jaina-mat-ānuraktāḥ||[5*] Tasya
Dēddulakō nāma sva-bhu-
- 7 j-ōpārijjita-śriyaḥ | sutō'=jani jan-ānanda-jananāj=janat-ārchchitaḥ||[6*] Tasy=ātmajō
vidita-sarva-kalā kalāpaḥ prāp=ādhipatyam=iha śilpishu Sarvvadēvaḥ | vēsm=
ātha Jainam=ati-sunda-
- ra[m=a]dvitīyam yō='chikarat=puravarē='pi cha **Siṅhapadrē**||[7*] Kurvāṇēn=
ātmanō='dhas=tribhuvana-vivara-vyāpinīm Viśvakarma-prakhyātim vāstu-vidyā
parichaya-chaturaiḥ śilpa-karm-ōpadēśaiḥ | vidy-ā-
- 9 rthinyā kṛitinyā purusha-parishadā sēvyamānēna nityam nāma svam sūtradhār-
ōpapada-vishayatām yēna dhanyēna nītam||[8*] Sandhy-ābhra-vidyuj-jala-
vudvu(bud-bu)d-augha-phēn-ōrmmi-gāndharva-pur-ēndra-chāpā-
- 10 n | vyati]tya mā]nushyam=anityam=ēvam vijñāya¹ Lakshmīm chapal-ātmikāñ=cha||
[9*] Ā[nī]tēna mahibhṛit=ātimahatā śrīmat-Pulindrēṇa sat-pūrvvē dēva-gṛīham
chikārayishatā tēn=ēdam=aty=āda-
- 11 [rāt] | ram[y]ē [Rā]jyapurē Purandara-pura-prakhyē svakiya-śriyā dēvaḥ
Śāntijinō='yam=uttama-mahā-kāyaḥ pratishṭhāpitaḥ|| [10*] Kāritaś=cha samuttuṅga-
śṛiṅg-ōttambhita-tāraḥ | śilāmayō='yam prā-
- 12 sādaḥ śarad-indu-kar-ōjva(jjva)laḥ|| [11*] Svarggād=ētaḍ=Draviṇapatinā prēshitam
marttya-lōkē [Śa]kr-ādēśād=ruchira-ruchinā kim svayam svam vimānam | n=ēdam
Mērōḥ śikhara-sadṛīśair=unnatair=udgha-kūṭair=Jai-
- 13 nam ha[r]mya[m] pihita-gaganam bhāti kētu-pratānaiḥ ||[12*] Ā-Kailāsa-girēr=
udagra-śikharād=ā-vāridhēḥ sat=taṭād=bhrāntvā Bhāratavarsham=ētaḍ=anagham
śaśvad=yaśōbhāsuram | puñjibhūya Jinēndra-chā-
- 14 ru-sadana-vyājēna Śakra-ālayam² ārōḍhum svayam=ichchhat=iḥva sutarām yat=Sārv-
vadēvam mahat|| [13*] Kārayitvā samuttuṅgam Śāntibhaṭṭarak-āspadam |
s-ākshaya-nīvi pūjāyai tad=aiv=ātha samarppi-
- 15 tam|| [14*] Śrī-Sūrasēn-āchāryasya jñāninō='ti tapasvinaḥ | vañijām gōshṭhikānān³-
cha tad-bhaktānām suchētasām|| [15*] Yāvad=dharmō Jina-nigaditō mōksha-
saukhya-pradāyī yāvan=Mērus=tridaśa-va-
- 16 nitā-sēvyamān-ōru-śriṅgaḥ | yāvat=sindhur=makara-nikar-ōllāsi-kallōla-mālas=tāvat=
sthēyād=idam=api śubham Śāntināthasya sadma ||[16*] Śrīmān=Sāgaraṇandī
vidvān=api Lōkadēva ity=asyā-
- 17 m | [dvā]v=apy=ētau sukavi vikhyātau sat=praśastāyām ||[17*] iti|| Samvat 979
Vaiśākha vadi 13 Bhaumē|| ||Om⁴[| *]Sransayan=bhūdharān ucchchaiḥ
kampō bhūmēr=abhūd=atha | chachāla tēn=ā-śikharād=ē

¹ There is an unnecessary *anusvāra* mark on *ya*.

² *Sandhi* is not observed here.

³ The letter *nā* is written below the line between two crosses and a cross is engraved above the letter *kā* to indicate the same.

⁴ Expressed by a symbol.

18 tat=sadma=samunnatam|| [18*] Mahā-matir=vva(bba)-bhūv=ātra Varāṅga=iti viśrutah |
tanayah Sarvva-dēvasya sarvva-vijñāni-nāyakah|| [19*] Yō var-āṅgō=py=anaṅgasya
sadṛīśatvam=avāptavān | bhāsvā-

19 [n=a]pi cha vāgīśah kalāvān=api yō vu(bu)-dhaḥ|| [20*] Yēn=ārthi-chātaka-vrātē
mahā-jaladha[rā]yitam | vāstu-vidy-ārtha-samśīti-gahanē dahanāyitam|| [21*]¹
Aśrāntam nṛipa-pūjitēna dhaninā mukhyēna vijñā² . . .

TRANSLATION³

Ōm | Obeisance to the Arhat.

(Verse 1) :—May Śānti Jinēndra always confer on you all the good things in life—Śānti Jinēndra who even being the veritable glorious full-moon (or having *mṛiga* as his *lāñchhana*) is ever flawless, who even being *nishkāma* (without any desire) was *pūrṇnakāma* (one who has fulfilled the desire of others) having granted rich gifts to others, and who even being always *dattārgha* (one to whom homage has been paid) by the learned became *anargha* (invaluable, high in esteem).⁴

(Verse 2) :—May Śāntinātha protect you | —Śāntinātha whose body that had never been a target of Cupid's arrows is resplendent, i.e. who has conquered Cupid, whose sovereign wealth (consists of) pure clear and shining knowledge that could view even the Lokālōka,⁵ whose feet are brightened by the multitude of rays emanating from the excellent jewels set in the loosened crown of the bowing (god) Indra who has approached (Śāntinātha) with devotion, who is an expert in the extirpation of enemies in the form of dreadful sins.

(Verse 3) :—May that king Mahipāla be victorious on this earth for long, at whose feet all the feudatories have respectfully placed their services. These are the sparks of the blazing fire of his prowess that shine forth all around at night in the form of stars.

(Verse 4) :—May the illustrious prince Sāvata of wide renown be victorious for long, who by his generosity, always fulfilling the desires of supplicants, is a veritable Karṇa ; who on the battle-field destroying the earth (*kau*) (for destroying the enemy forces reinforced by the Kauravas) is a veritable Bhīma ; and who also being endowed all over the body with auspicious signs (or accompanied everywhere by Lakshmaṇa?) is very much Rāma incarnate.

(Verse 5) :—There was a renowned person Ārdraṭa by name in the Dharkkaṭa family hailing from the glorious Pūrṇnatallaka. He was an expert in carving out various sculptures in stone and was attached to the Jaina faith.

(Verse 6) :—Ārdraṭa who had amassed wealth by dint of (labour and skill of) his arms begot a son named Dēddulaka, who on account of his being a source of delight to all people was respected by them.

¹ This incomplete verse seems to be in *Sārdūlavikrīḍita* metre.

² The record ends here abruptly. The intended reading seems to be *vijñāninā*.

³ The author has displayed his poetic excellence in the choice of diction. The *alamkāra* in this verse is *vvatirēka* based on *ślēsha*.

⁵ The word *Lōkālōka* means 'world and no world, the visible and invisible world'. It is also the 'name of a mythical belt or circle of mountains surrounding the outermost of the seven seas and dividing the visible world from the region of darkness'. Monier Williams : *A Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, s.v. *Lōkālōka* under *lōka* on p. 872. The term may also signify *lōkākāśa* and *Alōkākāśa* which, according to Jain Cosmographic conception, are the two parts of the space, the universe being situated in the former. This *Lōkākāśa* is composed of two entities of essences called *dharma* and *adharmā*, the substrata of motion and rest, conceived as the conditions for the presence of all existing beings. The *Alōkākāśa* is described as 'an absolute void impenetrable to anything, material and spiritual' (*JIH.*, Vol. XLVII, Pt. I, p. 53).

(Verse 7) :—His son Sarvādēva who had mastered all the fine arts in their entirety attained supremacy among the architects here. It was he who built the very beautiful and unique Jaina temple at the excellent town Simhapadra.

(Verse 8) :—He, the blessed one, who was always skilful attended upon by the assembly of persons who were his students, and who by his discourses on sculpture replete with the knowledge of the science of architecture outshone the fame of (the divine architect) Viśvakarmā which envelopes the three worlds had got his name always appended with the epithet *sūtradhāra*.

(Verse 9-11) :—Having realised that impermanence of the human existence surpasses (that of) the evening cloud, the lightening, bubble of water, the foam, the wave, the town of Gandharvas (an imaginary town in the sky) and the rainbow, and that fickle is the fortune he (Sarvādēva) who was brought by the great illustrious king¹ Pulindra and who was desirous of building a temple of a Jina(?) installed with devotion the excellent and lofty (image of) Jina Śānti (Śāntinātha) by his own wealth at the beautiful (town of) Rājyapura which equalled the town of (god) Indra, (i.e. Amarāvati), and caused to be built this stone temple glowing like the beams of the autumnal moon and supporting the stars with its lofty peak.

(Verse 12) :—Is it by the orders of Indra that the Lord of Wealth of radiant splendour has himself sent his own vehicle, from heaven to this mortal world? Oh! no; this is the Jaina temple covering the sky and shining by its spreading banners and lofty summits which are as high as the top of Mēru (mountain).

(Verse 13) :—The radiant, great, and eternal faultless glory of Sarvādēva after having travelled the whole of Bhāratavarsha from the high peaks of the mountain Kailāsa to the coast of the sea (now) collecting together very much longs to approach heaven (the abode of Indra) in the guise of the beautiful temple of Jinēndra.

(Verses 14-15) :—Having caused the lofty temple of Śāntibhaṭṭāraka to be built (Sarvādēva) entrusted it together with a permanent endowment for worship to the learned and great ascetic Sūrasēnāchārya and to the benevolent merchants who were members of a *gōshṭhi* (i.e. committee of supervisors in charge of the religious institution) and were devoted to him (i.e. Sūrasēnāchārya).

(Verse 16) :—May this auspicious abode of Śāntinātha stand as long as the dharma propagated by Jina, leading to emancipation and bliss (lasts), (as long as) the high peaked mountain Mēru enjoyed by the heavenly damsels and the sea (full of) waves (caused) by the multitudes of crocodiles (exist).

(Verse 17) :—The two famous and noble poets the illustrious Sāgaraṇandin and the learned Lōkadēva (have composed) this *praśasti* ||end|| Saṃvat 979 Tuesday, the 13th day of the dark fortnight of Vaiśākha||

Part II

(Verse 18) :—A mighty earthquake toppling down (even) the mountains occurred and on account of that this high building shook from top to the bottom.

¹ The meaning of the expression *sat-pūrvvē* is not clear.

(Verse 19) :—The wise, renowned, leader of all architects, Varāṅga, son of Sarvadēva, was born.

(Verse 20) :—He (Varāṅga), of beautiful limbs, resembled Cupid (or one devoid of limbs), though handsome (or the Sun) he was master of speech (or the planet Jupiter) and though a learned man (or the moon) he was wise (or the planet Mercury).

(Verse 21) :—Who was the very cloud for the *chātakas* in the form of supplicants, who was the very fire for the forest in the form of problems of Architecture.

(Verse 22) :—By the one, who was rich, held in high esteem by the king and chief among the architects.....

(Verse 18) :—It is by the orders of ladies that the Lord of Vastu of Indian splendor has himself sent his own temple from heaven to this mortal world. Oh! who is the Jain temple covering the sky and shining by its sparkling banners and jolly banners which are as high as the top of Meru (mountain).

(Verse 15) :—The radiant great and eternal faultless glory of Śaivadeva after having traversed the whole of Bhāratavāṣa from the high peaks of the mountains to the coast of the sea (now) collecting together very much logs to erect a temple (the stone of India) in the guise of the beautiful temple of Jambūdvīpa.

(Verse 14) :—Having raised the lofty temple of Śaivadeva to be built (Śaivadeva) entered it together with a permanent male woman for worship to the learned and great ascetic Śaivadeva and to the benevolent teachers who were members of a *gṛha* (the committee of supervisors in charge of the religious institution) and who served to him (Śaivadeva).

(Verse 12) :—My this auspicious stone of Jambūdvīpa stand as long as the *śaivadeva* pagoda by him, leading to emancipation and bliss (last), (as long as) the light peaked mountain Meru enjoyed by the heavenly damsels and the sea (full of) waves (conceal) by the mouths of crocodiles (etc.).

(Verse 17) :—The two diamonds and noble poets the illustrious Śaivadeva and the learned Iśvara (have composed) the *Varāṅga* and *Śaivadeva* (the 13th day of the dark fortnight of *Yajñikā*).

(Verse 13) :—A highly auspicious temple (even) the mountains omitted and on account of that this light peaked mountain (is) up to the bottom.

The meaning of the expression *śaivadeva* is not clear. ६ DDAVI